

Sommerfelds Fine-Structure-Constant and the pi derived Fine-Structure-Constant - what is the difference?

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Abstract

It is noticeable that there is a discrepancy between the Sommerfeld fine structure constant and the constant derived from the mathematical pi. It is to be discussed and considered why there is a difference between the both constants. Furthermore, it needs to be discussed what the relation is between the physical pi and the mathematical pi.

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The well-known fine structure constant has a value of $1/137.035999$. For the QED running coupling constant, this value corresponds to the asymptotic value for low energy densities.

In contrast, the constant derived from the mathematical pi gives a value of $1/137.028744$, a slightly higher value.

It is known and/or discussed that the fine structure constant has an energy dependence by itself, so that at high energies such as 90 GeV of the Z boson the coupling constant is $\alpha = 1/127$, a much higher value. As energy density increases, alpha also increases.

This would mean that alpha, derived from Pi, would correspond to an energy density slightly higher than the asymptotically lowest value, i.e. the energy density surrounding us.

This could suggest that the fine structure constant derived from pi would correspond to the actual original fine structure constant at a slightly higher energy density than the lowest possible. A possible option for this slightly higher energy density could be, for example the energy density that surrounds us now.

This could mean in turn that we are living in a flat part of the universe without any curvature.

In this respect, rest energies or rest masses of the particles are asymptotically low, ideal masses at extremely low energy densities. The real masses of the particles are slightly higher and can be calculated using the mathematical pi. These masses calculated with pi correspond to the real energy density of our real environment and to the real masses of the particles. However, we can also calculate the ideal rest masses of the particles by using the well-known fine structure constant.